

**22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling
for heavy duty hydrogen transport”**

Report A1.6.1

**Literature review of material compatibility studies undertaken in previous projects and their
experimental conditions**

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Submission date of the report: 28 September 2023

Revision date of the report: -

Summary

One of the most critical challenges for hydrogen sampling is to choose a cylinder in which the collected sample is not altered in any way, or more realistically in any avoidable way, during the process of collecting, transporting, or preparing the sample for analysis or measurement.

In this report, we discussed parameters that affect material compatibility: the suitability of the treatment for compounds present individually in the gas, the suitability of the treatment to avoid interactions between compounds, the effect of the filling pressure and the temperature on the stability, and the needs for pre-selection of cylinders. A general conclusion is that more studies are needed in order to better understand the effects of all these parameters, specifically for the filling pressure and the temperature. As long as these effects of the filling pressure has not been studied more extensively, stability studies shall be performed at pressures and temperatures similar to the ones used in the sampling strategies.

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1 Introduction

Sampling of hydrogen at a HRS shall be done so as the collected sample is not altered in any way, or more realistically in any avoidable way, during the process of collecting, transporting, or preparing the sample for analysis or measurement.

According to ISO 21087 [1], the sample should be collected at the HRS nozzle and be representative of the duration of the refuelling protocol. Due to the high pressure at the sampling point, cylinders are the most appropriate alternative for the sampling vessel.

One of the most critical decisions is the choice of the sampling cylinder as many parameters must be considered [2]:

- The vessels must be cleaned and evacuated before sampling,
- No loss of impurities shall occur during transportation (Timeline: 2-4 weeks maybe even longer if e.g., transported to Europe from USA or Asia)
- Sampling hydrogen may imply the presence of several species at the same time; it must be ensured that the vessel(s) is/are suitable for all impurities,
- The vessels need to be approved for transportation,
- The vessels need to be compatible with available hydrogen sampling devices developed to take samples at Hydrogen Refuelling Stations (HRSs)

Several compounds such as helium, nitrogen, argon are almost considered as inert and their concentration is expected to remain stable in any gas cylinder type. However, the material and the treatment of the cylinder are of special importance for reactive species (e.g., halogenated compounds, ammonia, formaldehyde, formic acid, carbon monoxide) and/or species that may adsorb onto the cylinder walls (e.g., water). The selection must be done to avoid losses occurring while the sample of hydrogen is collected at the HRS and transported to the laboratory. Losses due to reactions or adsorption within the vessels would lead to falsely lower levels of impurities being measured than are present in the original hydrogen.

To determine if a cylinder is suitable for a specific species, stability tests must be performed where the concentration changes are monitored and compared with the expected concentration for the duration of the test. The information gathered with this type of study can then be used to produce so-called tables of material compatibility which are very useful when choosing a sampling cylinder.

At the beginning of the MetroHyVe 2 project, a first table of material compatibility was produced and published [3]. Then during the project, new stability studies were conducted, and the table was updated as part of deliverable 5 [4].

Another issue highlighted by Arrhenius and al. was the terminology. For example, the definition of the term “suitable” would need to be defined quantitatively which was not the case in most of the studies used to produce the first table of material compatibility.

Finally, the last issue is the lack of information about the experimental conditions during the stability tests. For example, the filling pressure is not always specified, the change of pressure during the test is often not mentioned, the temperature is rarely specified (but it is assumed that the tests are done at ambient temperature).

In this report, we reviewed the material compatibility studies undertaken in previous projects and updated the material compatibility table, which was prepared in EMPIR JRP 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2,

with a list of experimental conditions and a list of parameters that affect material compatibility, including the filling pressure and the vessel's volume.

2 Terminology

More concrete definitions of several terms have been proposed by the MetroHyVe 2 project to better characterize the actual suitability of cylinder for hydrogen fuel sampling. Table 1 below is directly taken from 19ENG04 deliverable 5 [4].

Table 1. List of definition around cylinder suitability and stability for hydrogen fuel quality

<u>Suitable cylinder</u>	a suitable cylinder is a cylinder that allows the compounds to be stable for a 4-month period within a reasonable uncertainty and did not show any initial loss. It is a combination of stability and no initial loss.
<u>Stability</u>	a stable cylinder is a cylinder that had a consistent measured value of the contaminant of interest over the 4-month period within a reasonable uncertainty.
<u>Initial loss/increase</u>	an initial loss or increase is a significant difference in the amount fraction on first measurement compared to the gravimetric amount fraction that should be present in the cylinder (e.g., by adsorption to the cylinder walls).
<u>Unsuitable</u>	a cylinder that is deemed unsuitable for use for hydrogen sampling is a cylinder that has an initial change in amount fraction that could lead to false positives or negatives and/or is unable to keep the component of interest stable for a 4-month time.

A way to quantitatively establish suitability of cylinders is shown on Figure 1 which shows the percentage of contaminant amount fraction measured directly after preparation compared to the calculated gravimetric amount fraction together with the measurement uncertainty for different cylinders. The figure is extracted from [5].

Figure 1. Visual representation of cylinders suitability

3 Material compatibility tables

The latest material compatibility table was produced during the MetroHyVe2 project as part of 19ENG04 deliverable 5. The table 2 below is directly taken from the report (table 8)

Table 2. Summary of results from the MetroHyVe 2 WP2 and WP3 results for contaminants at amount fractions close to or at the ISO 14687 threshold values. The colour coding means green: suitable; yellow: suitable under limited conditions; red: unsuitable. Total sulphur has been assessed by taking the conservative approach. If one of the two sulphur compounds tested showed unsuitability, the overall cylinder was considered unsuitable.

Component	Steel				Aluminium								
	Stainless steel Sulfinert	Manganese steel	ALD-Coated steel	Untreated stainless steel	SPECTRA-SEAL	Untreated SGS	H2 Mobility	Aculife VIII	Aculife III	White top	AlphaTech	Performax	DB Gold
He	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	X	Suit	X	X	Suit
N ₂	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	Suit
Ar	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	X	Suit	X	X	Suit
CO ₂	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	X	Suit	X	X	Suit
CO	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit
Tot S	Uns, Stab**	Uns, Stab*	Uns, IL	i.d.	Uns, IL-stab	Uns, Stab**	Uns, IL-stab	i.d.	Uns, IL-stab	Uns, Stab**	Uns, IL-stab		Uns,stab†
H ₂ S	Uns, Stab**	Uns, Stab*	Uns, IL	i.d.	Uns, IL-stab	Uns, Stab**	Uns, IL-stab	i.d.	Uns, IL-stab	Uns, Stab**	Uns, IL-stab	i.d.	Suit†
OCS	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Uns,stab
HCl	Uns, IL-Stab	Uns, IL-stab	Uns, IL-stab	i.d.	Suit	Uns, IL-stab	Uns, IL-stab	i.d.	Uns, IL-stab	Uns, IL	Uns, IL-stab	i.d.	Suit
CCl ₂ H ₂	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit
CH ₂ O	Suit	Uns, Stab*	Uns, stab**	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	Suit
CH ₂ OH	Suit	Uns, IL-Stab	Uns, IL	i.d.	Suit	Uns, IL-stab	Uns, IL-stab	i.d.	Uns, IL	Uns, IL	Uns, IL	i.d.	Suit
NH ₃	Suit	Uns, IL-Stab	Uns, stab	i.d.	Uns, IL	Uns, IL	Suit	i.d.	Suit	Uns, IL	Uns, IL-stab	i.d.	Suit
O ₂	Suit ^a	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit ^a	Suit ^a	Suit ^a	i.d.	i.d.	Suit ^a	i.d.	i.d.	Suit ^a
H ₂ O	Suit ^b	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit ^b	Suit ^b	Suit ^b	i.d.	i.d.	Suit ^b	i.d.	i.d.	Suit ^b
C ₃ H ₈	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit
CH ₄	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	X	Suit	X	X	Suit
C ₂ H ₆	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	X	Suit	X	X	Suit

X should be suitable (no published data available)

i.d. insufficient data

^a Oxygen stability seems to vary between cylinders of same internal treatment.

^b Oxygen reactivity may affect the amount fraction of water through the reaction in hydrogen matrix.

† Additional sulphur containing components were present in the gas cylinder

Suit Stable to gravimetric amount fraction within 95% confidence level for duration of the study (4 months)

Uns Unsuitable for sampling this compound at EN 17124 amount fraction

IL Unsuitability due to an initial loss of the compound compared to gravimetric value

Stab Unsuitability due to compound instability in the cylinder for the duration of the study

* Unstable but suitable for very short time (1-2 week), stability uncertainty including decay is similar to stable cylinders for this period. The stability period is provided in brackets, only useful for very short transport

** Unstable but suitable for short time (1-2 month), stability uncertainty including decay is similar to stable cylinders for this period. The stability period is provided in brackets, only useful for short transport

4 Experimental conditions applied during suitability studies

Unfortunately, comprehensive information about the experimental conditions applied during suitability studies is often lacking.

For example, Silcotek has published a technical report [6] showing the stability of 17 ppb in SilcoNert 2000-coated cylinders and in uncoated stainless-steel cylinder for a period of 7 days. However, in the report, the matrix, the size of the cylinder, the filling pressure, the temperature, the configuration of the cylinders (one or two valves) were not indicated.

EffecTech, in partnership with Luxfer Gas Cylinders Ltd., assessed the performance of SGS cylinders compared to a basic (B) aluminium alloy cylinder and a cylinder that had been acid washed (AW) [7] for the stability of 0.5 ppm of H₂S in synthetic air for a period of 100 days. However, in the report, the size of the cylinder, the filling pressure, the temperature, the configuration of the cylinders (one or two valves) were not indicated.

These studies were not directly linked to hydrogen sampling at a HRS.

The most relevant studies performed to establish cylinder's suitability for assessment of hydrogen purity at a HRS were done in the MetroHyVe 1 and MetroHyVe2 projects. The filling pressure was 100 bar for the cylinders except in the case where the cylinders were larger than 10L water volume. The cylinder pressure for a 30L was filled to 50 bar and a 47L cylinder was filled to the same volume of gas as the 10L cylinder at 100 bar (so 1000L of gas filling to about 20 bar).

The cylinders were all above 10 bar at the end of the tests, most were much higher, except the 2.25L cylinder for the acidic set with water measurement which, due to the larger number of analysis and low starting volume of the cylinder, ran empty when a repeat measurement was made on water after all analytes had been run. The exact pressure was not monitored as the measurements were being run for each cylinder.

Most stability studies evaluated the performance of the cylinder for one specific condition, but other parameters such as the impact of pressure on the stability of components has never been evaluated.

5 Parameters affecting material compatibility

5.1 Cylinders material and treatment

MetroHyVe 2 project produced a first material compatibility at the beginning of the project [3]. Using the outcomes from new stability studies, the table was updated [4] and is now a very comprehensive (see table 2) which gives a good guide for sampling strategies developers.

5.2 Presence of several compounds in the cylinders at the same time

Most of the suitability studies have been done for one compound only (or several compounds from the same family such as sulfur compounds). Therefore, several recent studies performed as part of MetroHyVe2 have tackled the possible issue of interactions when several species are presence simultaneously and looked if the cylinder has some influence on these interactions.

Stability studies were performed in two 10 L cylinder types (SPECTRA-SEAL aluminium, SGS aluminium [5]) for four different mixtures in hydrogen. The first mixture was chosen to represent all gaseous impurities to be measured in ISO 14687:2022 [8]: carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, methane, ethane, nitrogen, argon, helium, ammonia, formic acid, formaldehyde, hydrogen sulphide, dichloromethane, water, and oxygen. The second mixture contains the same compounds except oxygen and water, the third mixture contained the same compounds as mixture 1 except oxygen, water, ammonia, formic acid, and formaldehyde and the fourth mixture contained the same compounds as mixture 1 except ammonia, formaldehyde, and water [4].

Carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, nitrogen, helium, argon, methane, ethane, oxygen, water and dichloromethane remained stable in hydrogen in both the SGS™ aluminium cylinder and the SPECTRA-SEAL® aluminium for 4 months (the duration of the study). This implies that contaminants listed above do not experience interference with each other in a hydrogen matrix in the cylinder types tested. The presence of water at amount fractions close to the ISO 14687 threshold did not seem to affect the stability of carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide despite these contaminants considered as having possible interactions with the water.

Both types of cylinders showed complete loss of ammonia amount fraction within 24 h.

Stability issues were observed for hydrogen sulphide, ammonia, formaldehyde, and formic acid.

Hydrogen sulphide had already disappeared from the SPECTRA-SEAL® aluminium cylinder when the initial measurement was performed while no initial loss was observed in the SGS™ aluminium cylinder where hydrogen sulphide concentration remained stable for the duration of the study.

The SGS™ finish aluminium cylinder showed complete loss of formic acid amount fraction within 48 h. No initial loss of formic acid was seen in the SPECTRA-SEAL® aluminium cylinder.

Both cylinder types had initial losses of formaldehyde after 24 h and no measurable amount fraction of formaldehyde at 9 days. It is important, therefore, that measurements for formaldehyde are done within 24 h so that any loss in formaldehyde amount fraction is minimised, but even then, the results can be unrepresentative.

Some of the results of the stability of components varied with and without water in the gas [4]. Formic acid and formaldehyde stability improve in some cylinders when 5 µmol/mol water is present (water is used as a stabilising agent for formaldehyde).

Ammonia (activity 2.2) was shown to react both with formaldehyde and formic acid in any cylinder type. This would mean that if an HRS has both ammonia and formaldehyde or formic acid in the sample gas, these contaminants would disappear from the gas by reaction and only reaction products will be found in the gas. Ammonia is known to react with formic acid to form ammonia formate which is soluble in water. This particular case is not related to the cylinder type.

The results of these studies therefore demonstrate that interactions between contaminants in the same cylinder are possible but limited to water, ammonia, formaldehyde, and formic acid. Such cross reactivity and potential by-products need to be understood and differentiated from stability issues.

5.3 Filling pressure

Very few studies have been done to evaluate the effect of the filling pressure on the stability of species stored in cylinders. However, stability studies for species in biomethane [9] show that stability was found to be better when the gas is stored at higher pressure (60 bar against 8 bar). The assumption is that it will be a fixed number of molecules required to occupy the active sites on the inner surface of the cylinder. At lower pressure, this would be a larger proportion of the total number of molecules available compared to higher pressure. Therefore, an indication of the filling pressure applied when doing stability studies is of high importance. In the case of hydrogen sampling, tests at high pressure (>70 bar) are preferred as this condition is close to the filling pressure actually used during the sampling.

As shown during the review of sampling strategies [3], the size of the cylinders and the filling pressure of cylinders varies from sampling devices to sampling devices, but the filling pressure is at least around 70 bar or higher. This information is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Cylinder's size and filling pressure for the different sampling strategies currently in use

Sampling strategies	Cylinder's size (L)	Filling pressure (bar)
Air Liquide	5	150
ASTM D7606:17	0.5 - 2	69
Gas direct	47	Max 120
Engie Device	1	90
Linde qualitizer	10	90-130
Hy-SaM	2.25 or 10	90

5.4 Temperature

Studying the impact of temperature onto compounds stability in gas cylinder is complex to realise. A recent study of Bacquart *et al.* [10] showed stability of formic acid in hydrogen at 4 °C. The study was limited to one week. The cylinder was immersed in a water bath maintained at low temperature.

Low temperature is often expected to improve stability however gas sample may have different behaviour at low temperature. Temperature study may be critical especially because temperature in the cylinder while sampling hydrogen changes depending on the season or on the refuelling condition (precooling or not) and varies from 4 °C (parallel sampling with precooling refuelling) up to 40 °C (gas serial sampling with large cylinder).

5.5 Cylinder selection

Preselection of cylinders can be needed for some impurities. For example, decay of oxygen amount fraction can occur at different rates within cylinders of the same internal treatment. [5].

Studies of cylinders aging were performed during MetroHyVe2 [4] showing decrease in performance but the lifetime of cylinder passivation types for hydrogen fuel sampling requires further investigation.

5.6 Sampling material compatibility

Sampling systems have been mostly built out of stainless-steel materials. Passivation for such materials is available (e.g., sulfinert, silconert2000) however there is limited study on the importance or benefit of the passivation especially for low level of reactive compounds (e.g., hydrogen sulphide, ammonia). Other non-metallic materials (e.g., high pressure plastic hose, valve parts) may be used for sampling systems, however there is limited knowledge on the impact of these materials on the hydrogen gas composition especially for reactive gases or water.

6 Conclusion

The current practice for assessing hydrogen purity, according to ISO 14687, involves sampling. The measurement uncertainty associated with the sampling is the single most important parameter that describes the quality of the measurements, and it must inevitably contribute to the uncertainty associated with the reported result. The use of correct sampling techniques is an important safety and quality critical step in gas analysis. A representative sample should be an unbiased reflection of the gas to analyse i.e., it shall have the same composition as the gas it is attributed to.

One of the most critical challenges for hydrogen sampling is to choose a cylinder in which the collected sample is not altered in any way, or more realistically in any avoidable way, during the process of collecting, transporting, or preparing the sample for analysis or measurement.

In this report, we discussed parameters that affect material compatibility:

- First and foremost, suitability of the treatment must be established for compounds present individually in the gas: recent studies [4] have shown that DB Gold and Sulfinert stainless steel were the most suitable cylinders but even these are not suitable for all gaseous components to analyse for hydrogen purity, a combination of at least two cylinder types may be necessary; the most challenging compounds are sulfur compounds (at least hydrogen sulphide and carbonyl sulphide) but some issues have been observed with hydrogen chloride, ammonia, formic acid and formaldehyde
- Suitability of the treatment to avoid interactions between compounds should then be studied: the presence of some compounds may stabilize other compounds (such as water for formic acid and formaldehyde), the presence of some compounds may lead to cross-interactions. However, these effects are not always related to the cylinder itself, but sometimes only to the compounds; The results of studies showed that interactions between contaminants in the same cylinder may happen, but only with water, ammonia, formaldehyde, and formic acid. Such cross reactivity and potential by-products need to be understood and differentiated from stability issues,
- Filling pressure: previous studies have shown that the filling pressure may have an influence on material compatibility as it is assumed that a fixed number of molecules are required to occupy the active sites on the inner surface of the cylinder. At lower pressure, this would be a larger proportion of the total number of molecules available compared to higher pressure. As long as the effect of the filling pressure has not been studied more extensively, stability studies

shall be performed at pressures similar to the ones used in the sampling strategies (not less than 70 bar and up to 150 bar).

- Temperature in the cylinder: not enough studies have been done to draw conclusions about the effect of the temperature on the stability of components, however lower temperatures are expected to improve stability.
- Cylinder selection: Preselection of cylinders may be needed for some impurities (e.g. oxygen decay occurring at different rates within cylinders of the same internal treatment). Decrease in treatment/cylinder's performance have been shown over time but the lifetime of cylinder passivation types for hydrogen fuel sampling requires further investigation.

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